

DETERMINING THE EFFECT OF WATER-SOLUBLE CORROSION INHIBITORS ON IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF CRUDE OIL AND GAS PIPELINES

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Abstract. *In this article, laboratory tests were conducted to determine the effectiveness of corrosion inhibitors containing nitrogen and phosphorus based on gossypol resin using the gravimetric method and the degree of inhibition of corrosion inhibitors using polarization curves using a CS-350 potentiostat device. It was investigated that the level of corrosion protection was improved from 60-65% to 93-98.4%.*

Keywords: *gossypol resin, corrosion inhibitors, gravimetric method, potentiostat device, main oil and gas pipelines, inhibitor efficiency, corrosion rate.*

Introduction: The corrosion process is one of the main factors influencing the efficiency of main oil and gas pipelines, directly affecting economic costs [1; 2]. As a result of corrosion processes, the performance of certain metal structures, pipelines, and other equipment [3; 4] is significantly affected, impacting the quality and productivity of the manufacturing process [5; 6].

To address these issues, we developed corrosion inhibitors based on water-soluble gossypol resin containing nitrogen and phosphorus, and we recommend applying these inhibitors to improve the efficiency of main oil and gas pipelines by determining their effectiveness in preventing corrosion in aqueous environments.

During the research process, the efficiency of the corrosion inhibitors was determined using the gravimetric method and by analyzing polarization curves with the CS-350 potentiostat device to measure the degree of inhibition.

The gravimetric method is widely used in laboratory conditions to determine the corrosion rate and the degree of protection of metals. In this method, the mass loss difference between the sample of the metal tested in the environment with and without inhibitor is used to determine the corrosion rate.

Additionally, experiments were conducted at various temperatures and concentrations ranging from 200 mg/l to 1000 mg/l to determine the corrosion rate. The effectiveness of various inhibitors was determined at different intervals, ranging from 48 hours to 240 hours. For this, experiments were carried out to determine the corrosion rate of a steel electrode in different concentration and temperature ranges.

The corrosion inhibitors based on water-soluble gossypol resin, containing nitrogen and phosphorus, were tested for their effectiveness (Z%) and the degree of corrosion in various environments and concentrations. The test environments included water, sodium sulfate, sodium sulfide, sodium bicarbonate, sodium hypochlorite, sodium carbonate, potassium chloride, and other solutions.

Initially, the effectiveness of the corrosion inhibitors was determined in these solutions. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Corrosion rate and protection levels of corrosion inhibitors based on water-soluble gossipol resin containing nitrogen and phosphorus in different environments.

Experimental environment	Indicators	Control sample	corrosion inhibitor
H ₂ O	K	4,0828	0,01907
	Z	-	98,4
Na ₂ SO ₄ (3%)	K	4,14	0,3402
	Z	-	94,8
Na ₂ S (3%)	K	4,013	0,058
	Z	-	97,6
NaHCO ₃ (3%)	K	4,47	0,787
	Z	-	98,24
NaClO (3%)	K	4,075	0,0747
	Z	-	95,4
Na ₂ CO ₃ (3%)	K	4,26	0,122
	Z	-	98,1
KCl	K	4,76	0,453
	Z	-	97,9
K ₂ SO ₄ ·MgSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O (3%)	K	4,64	0,74
	Z	-	96,8
MgSO ₄ ·KCl·H ₂ O (3%)	K	4,089	0,0181
	Z	-	96,1
CaCl ₂ (3%)	K	4,68	0,637
	Z	-	95,4
MgCl ₂ (3%)	K	4,72	0,2756
	Z	-	97,6
MgSO ₄ (3%)	K	4,26	0,560
	Z	-	93,4

* **K**, (g/cm²·s) – corrosion rate; **Z** %, – protection level.

In Table 1, the protection levels of corrosion inhibitors based on gossipol resin, which contains nitrogen and phosphorus, in various environments were determined as a result of the research. The corrosion inhibitors based on gossipol resin, which contains nitrogen and phosphorus, were used at concentrations of up to 3% in the solutions. The best results were achieved for this inhibitor, with the corrosion protection level improving from 60-65% to 93-98.4%.

The effectiveness of corrosion inhibitors was studied using the CS-350 potentiostat device, through polarization curves, to examine the mechanism and effectiveness of the inhibitors. This method allows for determining the inhibition effectiveness by the difference in potential between the metal sample in inhibitor and non-inhibitor environments. The current applied to the process is also referred to as the corrosion current. In environments with corrosion inhibitors, the amount of corrosion current significantly decreases due to the inhibition of the metal electrode surface.

Electrochemical experiments were conducted on samples of St3 steel in the form of plates. The Ag/AgCl solution was used as the reference electrode. In this case, inhibitors were used at concentrations of 1-3%.

Figure 1: Polarization curves of St3 steel at different concentrations of a corrosion inhibitor based on gossipol resin containing nitrogen and phosphorus in a graded aqueous medium, at $303 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 hours.

Table 2: Effectiveness of the corrosion inhibitor based on gossipol resin containing nitrogen and phosphorus, determined by the polarization curve method, at $298 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ temperature in a graded aqueous medium.

Inhibitor	C, (mg/l)	i, (mA/sm ²)	Γ	θ	η , (%)
brine solution	-	$0,84 \pm 0,14$	-	-	-
Corrosion inhibitor	100	$0,41 \pm 0,13$	7,14	0,8142	81,42
	200	$0,21 \pm 0,08$	9,11	0,8814	88,14
	300	$0,14 \pm 0,01$	11,61	0,9175	91,75
	400	$0,06 \pm 0,005$	13,84	0,9576	95,76

In Table 2, when the effectiveness of the corrosion inhibitors based on water-soluble gossipol resin containing nitrogen and phosphorus was studied using the electrochemical method of polarization curve analysis in a grading aqueous environment, it was found to be 95.76%.

The corrosion current in the environment without the inhibitor and with the inhibitor in the grading aqueous medium differed significantly. In the case of the corrosion inhibitor based on water-soluble gossipol resin containing nitrogen and phosphorus, the corrosion current value decreased from 0.84 ± 0.14 i (mA/cm²) to 0.06 ± 0.005 i (mA/cm²) at a concentration of 400 mg/l.

Thus, it was determined that corrosion inhibitors based on gossipol resin, containing nitrogen and sulfur, are effective in protecting against corrosion in aqueous environments, both in open and closed atmospheric conditions.

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